

FUTURE SCHOOL TEACHERS SHOULD BE PREPARED FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES BY USING INNOVATIVE TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES.

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Annotation: The analysis of work aimed at developing the practical competence of future teachers and the presentation of a technologically developed model for improving the practical competence of future teachers in general education institutions are presented.

Keywords: professional, competence, technology, digitization, function, component, procedural

In modern professional educational institutions in Uzbekistan, especially in pedagogical colleges, it is necessary to develop critical thinking in order to solve various emerging issues in an adaptive manner, independently acquire necessary knowledge, and effectively apply them in practice. It is also important to find ways to resolve emerging issues, understand the problems that actually arise, and solve them in a rational manner using modern technologies, as well as develop new goals, exercise creative thinking, and improve skills in working with information.

Therefore, developing the professional competence of teachers in general education institutions is currently one of the most important tasks.

Our research has shown that modeling the preparation of future teachers for professional activities by first using innovative teaching technologies to develop practical competence is crucial.

The educational environment greatly influences the intellectual, social, physical, and mental development of students. Creating a safe environment promotes students' desire to acquire knowledge. Adapting the learning environment to the specific needs of students encourages them to work independently and collaboratively, participate in various activities and assignments, become responsible and actively engage in the learning process, and take on more complex tasks in daily situations.

In our research, we first develop a technological model for shaping the professional competencies of teachers in future school education organizations. By the technological model in the research, we mean the project-based pedagogical process in all its components - content, in a way that ensures achieving the desired result, in the process of reading and teaching, in educational tools - is understood as reaching the project's educational goal.

The theoretical basis for developing a technological model for shaping the professional competencies of teachers in future school education includes the following: directing students towards a complete and accurate perception of future work activities, helping students to fulfill their main professional tasks in specially created conditions, integrating students' educational and professional activities through the functional tasks of the teacher, ensuring students' professional-theoretical and professional-practical readiness.

As mentioned above, the overall readiness for theoretical and practical training for future work is manifested in the accumulation of competencies based on knowledge and skills. Modeling professional activity in the educational process serves as a technology that helps prepare specialists with a high level of professional competence for secondary education organizations.

A.I. Sherbakov paid attention to the necessity of using modeling in the process of preparing pedagogical personnel. He wrote: "...young professionals may be well acquainted with the theoretical principles of psychology, pedagogy, and teaching methods, but they do not possess practical pedagogy, that is, the "technology" of pedagogical education and upbringing, which can be called a rule. Of course, this deep understanding of such "technology" is only possible based on extensive experience working with children. Therefore, the foundations of successful teaching activity, at least initially, should be established by establishing a more substantial connection between pedagogical theory and practice."

The role and importance of modeling in preparing students for professional activity are determined by the unique characteristics of pedagogical expertise. In order to effectively manage children's activities based on clear goals and psychological-pedagogical conditions, taking into account each child's individual development and personal formation, students need to have procedural didactic skills. Modeling allows students to be equipped with pedagogical methods of influencing actions, both in various situations with children, their parents, and colleagues, through artificially created conditions.

In our concept, which encompasses all of the above, we can outline the following: a technologically developed curriculum that aims to enhance the practical competence of future teachers in college-level educational institutions, the use of modeling professional activities in the learning process, and the superior role of the teacher's teaching function - which helps to achieve high results in teaching and allows for the practical implementation of the developed pedagogical system.

The technologically developed model for enhancing the practical competence of future teachers in college-level educational institutions includes the following components: goal-oriented component; content component; process component (1 - diagram).

The vocational activity of the "Information Technologies in Vocational Activities" subject, which is an integral part of the unchanging section of the educational standard-04.11.02.02 for pedagogical colleges, performs a substantive component task.

In teaching the subject "Information Technologies in Vocational Activities," students learn the following: the role of computers as tools for information processing, the place of computer programs and their use in information processing, the classification and composition of personal computers, system blocks and their structure, organizing and storing information on computers; creating didactic games for various activities conducted in vocational training centers (VTC); using electronic textbooks; finding professional information from the internet; teaching primary computer literacy to primary school children in vocational activities effectively; searching for information from the internet, organizing, structuring, generalizing, and presenting information in a comprehensible form; teaching children to work on computers using computer games and didactic games; utilizing existing software on computers to prepare materials suitable for children's age; acquiring knowledge in the use of multimedia technology and telecommunication tools, as well as installing software on computers; working with new versions of the WINDOWS operating system; working with operating systems and programs working under its control; working with the main and additional computer equipment; working with information on computers, organizing and storing data; using office software packages and utilizing the capabilities of modern text processors; creating didactic games related to the topic using practical software on computers; gathering and reworking professional information, using the internet and electronic textbooks during training sessions; shaping practical skills in primary computer literacy in primary school children; shaping practical skills in primary computer literacy in primary school children through interactive activities with practical programs; acquiring skills in using multimedia technology and telecommunication tools related to specialization through practical activities.

As it stands, the development of practical competence in the field of "Information Technologies in Vocational Activities" serves to enhance the necessary practical competence for teachers of secondary education institutions.

The distinctive feature of the procedural component is the use of educational and professional tasks that reflect typical situations that arise in the teacher's actual practice. The main pedagogical technology for modeling students' future work activity is through the implementation of specific actions in certain conditions.

The term "task" implies the understanding of a specific goal set under certain conditions that can be achieved by carrying out certain actions.

The pedagogical significance of educational tasks is significant. Firstly, they help students to model their future professional activity through "implementation". Secondly, they facilitate the process of internalizing students' main functional tasks for the future: any situation in real pedagogical practice is described with various conditions that require consideration of multiple factors and decision-making. This can only be accomplished by an experienced teacher. The importance of educational task-models lies in their ability to direct students' attention to predetermined situations, thereby simplifying decision-making. Additionally, they reduce students' subjective concerns about potential mistakes. Thirdly, they provide the teacher with the opportunity to quickly implement and evaluate conclusions

made by students in specific situations created by them, as the process of resolving educational issues is carried out with direct participation and supervision of the teacher.

In the teaching process, it is necessary to adhere to the following principles when using educational and professional tasks:

1. The collection of tasks should fully cover all the content of vocational activities, meaning that standard professional tasks should correspond to its main composition.

2. The location of each task and the time for its implementation are determined based on theoretical material that provides information support, which means that when modeling professional activities during the learning process, it is necessary to analyze not only the content of the topic but also the usual professional tasks that decompose and analyze the professional activity itself, starting from the final goal, i.e., the implementation of professional activity, to the initial stages - individual operations and actions of the specialist. The loading of professional activity on the subject matter of the educational subject allows for the following: firstly, to determine the actual place of each professional task in the learning process, which is related to the theoretical readiness for its implementation; secondly, to identify not only the shortcomings in practical activities but also the importance of the presented educational information.

3. The tasks should reflect and generalize the most important aspects of vocational activity, meaning that they should identify and present the main (important) indicators that allow for the allocation and presentation of these indicators during the process of problem-solving for students, both in solving problems and making decisions in subsequent professional activities.

4. It is necessary to find the most appropriate method for imitating each element of vocational activity: practicing, analyzing situations, solving problems, role-playing games, etc. Before choosing a method, it is necessary to evaluate its effectiveness compared to other teaching methods. In evaluation, first and foremost, it is necessary to consider the conformity of the formed ability to the ability required in practical activity.

After generalizing the above statements, we can conclude the following: the technologically developed model of improving the practical competence of future teachers of preschool educational institutions contributes to the integration of their knowledge and professional activities into the educational process, ensuring the formation of a certain quality among students. The teacher, who participates in the continuous planning and organizational activities, serves as a guarantee for achieving the goal of shaping this quality.

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